

“INVESTORS PERCEPTION AND PATTERN OF INVESTMENT IN STOCK MARKET INSTRUMENTS – A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHENNAI CITY”

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
	<p>Bombay stock exchange usually famous for equity Market. It is the oldest stock Market in India. Every investor Purchase the stock for a Margin of Profit or double the capital or wealth building. But, before Creating wealth there are several factors must determine for stock selection. One must considered all these factors for purchasing the equity share. Even after considered all these factors, Market cannot be predicted it is totally high risky than other financial instruments. In this study, the researcher attempt how the Chennai based investors choosing the right stock (equity share) for their wealth creation even after determining several factors. This study given an eye opener for the stock market beginners, those who are ready to invest but do not know how to select and analyses the equity share in stock exchange.</p>

Key Words: Understanding Stock Market, Other Financial Instruments, Investors Investment Mindset, Satisfaction in Return on Invest

INTRODUCTION:

Stock Market plays a significant role in Economic Development. Stock Market facilitates the Mobilization of funds from small investors and channelizes these resources into various sectors for high returns and economic growth. With an aim to regulate securities market in India Government of India setup a regulatory Body called SEBI. The main aim of SEBI is to protect the investors in securities matter and regulate the securities market. Now-a-days the securities of shareholders are held in electronic form through the medium of Depository Participation. A “DP” can be Bank, Financial institution, Broker or any eligible entities as per SEBI Guidelines are complied with the act. Before 1996, in India the shares are Purchased, Sale, Transfer of Shares is done in Physical form which is highly unsafe and it’s a huge problem for investors. Every depository must register with SEBI to commence its business. In India these are two types of Depositories. (NSDL & CDSL)

NSDL - National Securities Depository Limited

CDSL- Central Depository Service Limited

The Operational and Functional issues relating to depository systems are primary governed by the done electronically and no Physical/Paper work is involved. The Depository System is used for Purchase/Transfer/Sale of Securities.

India got freedom in 1947 but Corporate India got freedom on 1991 (LPG era) before that License era. After 1991, foreign companies have the equity share of up to 24% in Indian Companies and also the lock-in period of their investment is reduced from 3 years to 1 year.

Investing in stock market is investing in business. The first thing in investing in Indian stock market is understand our economy and business.

Going back to history before 1991, there will be one car – Ambassador, one scooter – Bajaj Chetak, one watch – HMT. This era was called license era. As mentioned in earlier the companies in manufacturing sector have to get many licenses to Manufacture and also they must be in limit to produce only limited units.

Finally corporates got freedom in 1991 by implementing new policies in LPG. Bringing excellence in Technology and R&D, the Service sector will rule the world especially India. We made large IT organizations and 1000's of BPO. After 2000 (Internet era) everything started utilizing computer with internet. Now the advancement reaches to mobile phone with internet with touch screens.

Even after 28 years of corporate India only limited sectors got developed still a lot has to be getting to develop. The stock market is also called a capital market. As through the stock market, companies raise capital to finance their business.

In capital market / stock market, a stock broker plays a vital role. They are the one who plays well to connect the shares of company to the general public who are subscribing their shares. Like already said every transaction is in a Demat mode, so every investor needs (DP) Depository Participation to fulfill their transaction in stock market.

Stock market has many investors, out of that warren buffet, Rajesh Jhunjhunwala, are few well known investors. As same it has many losers, one must be patience in stock market while investing after analyzing the company for investing their hard earned money for long term.

FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS:

Financial instruments are the evidence of ownership of part of something as in Stocks, shares, etc. and also it has a contractual right to receive cash. Some of the Indian financial instruments are:

- Direct equity stocks
- Direct Equity Stocks
- Mutual Funds (Equity, Debt, Hybrid, ELSS, Liquid Funds)
- Future & Options
- Currencies & Commodities
- PPF
- Post Office Savings

- NSC
- Debentures & Bonds
- Bank Deposits
- Gold
- Insurance

The above few financial instruments in India have its own advantage and disadvantage. One must be very cautious while investing in above. The above few instruments are having fixed returns and few are below the inflation rate while the stock markets are subject the market risk.

Direct Equity Stocks:

Direct equity stock investments are very rewarding and at the same time there will be a heavy loss also before investing once must analyze the company. This can be possible for a highly available person like CA, but everyone can easily identified the company in very few steps which will be discussed in further chapters of the study. People who can balance the risk and returns are the real winners in direct equity stock.

Mutual Funds:

A mutual fund is a Mechanism of pooling fund in small amount from investors and invests in companies of direct stock. A mutual fund is required to be registered with SEBI before it can collect funds from the public.

How Mutual Fund works and How Public / Investor gained?

Let assume MRF Company per share cost Rs.70, 000/-. A small investor can invest only Rs.1000/- like that aggregation of 70 small investors with Rs.1000/- can invest in one MRF Company share. At final every 70 investors get 0.01429 equal units in MRF Company. The value of one unity in MF is on given date and the value called NAV (Net Asset Value). At Present there are 44 Mutual Funds in India.

S.No	Types of Fund House	No. of M.F
1.	Bank Sponsored	7
2.	Indian – Public Sector	2
3.	Indian – Private Sector	19
4.	Indian – Foreign Joint Venture	11
5.	Foreign	5
Total		44

The Mutual Fund has various types of funds they are mentioned below but every fund has its own direct scheme and regular scheme and also the fund has growth option and dividend option.

Direct Scheme is the scheme which the investors invest directly through AMC (Asset Management Company). The investment is fulfilled by submitting the OTM (One Time Mandate), Application form, with the proof of identity (Aadhar & PAN) and a cheque leaf with name mentioned in leaf.

Regular Schemes the scheme while the investor approaches the MFD (Mutual Fund Distributor – usually certified by AMFI – Association of Mutual funds of India with an ARN Number) for the Mutual fund investment. Here the risk is reducing because the MFD analyze the fund which suits the investors Performa. Based on the investor details the Fund may vary. There are:

- Equity Fund
- Debt Fund
- Hybrid Fund
- Tax / ELSS Fund
- Liquid Fund

a) Equity Fund

Equity Funds are the funds which are invested in equity shares and related securities. They have the potential to delivery high returns during long term could be relatively volatile in short term. Equity funds will be large capital funds few are in

and small capital funds.

b) Debt Fund

These funds invest in corporate Debentures, government securities and other such debt instruments. It may deliver returns in line with inflation or marginally higher than inflation. Debt funds would be less volatile than equity funds in short run.

c) Hybrid Fund

Hybrid funds are also called balanced funds. These funds balance the mix of equity and debt funds. This gives the decent returns to the investors and the main aim of these funds later to both the investment needs of investor – fixed income and also the growth orientation.

d) ELSS / Tax Fund

These funds have tax rebates under 80C in Income Tax Act 1961. These funds have 3 years lock-in Period. Investors invest in Tax Funds/ Equity Linked Saving Schemes (ELSS) because of government offers tax benefits and also better return on investment.

e) Liquid Fund

Liquid fund invest in Debt instrument and money market instruments. These funds tenure up to 90 days nearly 3 months however a investor park the surplus fund in liquid fund up to the amount of Rs.10 lakhs.

In Short NAV of liquid funds is calculated for 365 days rest other funds NAV is calculated only for the Business days.

Future & Options (F&O):

Future is a right to obligate the buy/sell the stock at predetermined amount and time of delivery whereas options are the right without an obligation to buy/sell the stock. Options are in 2 types; they are call option and put option. Call option which means for right to buy and Put option refers to right to sell. Future and options are traded in contract of 1/2/3 months. But all the F&O contracts will expire on the last Thursday of the Month. Futures will trade at a Future Price which is normally a

premium price.

Let Assume 1500 SRF shares at the price of Rs.3000 so the value will be 45lakhs for one lot (1500 shares). Here in future the investor will buy the 20% margin of SRF shares which is only 9 lakhs for 1500 shares. Here if the price goes up the leverage will be 5 times of profit whereas the loss (Price reduces) will be the same of 5 times of his investments.

An option is a right without obligation so the investor can buy 400 SRF shares call option at price of Rs.10. Since one lot be (1500 shares). The maximum loss will be Rs.15, 000 (1500x10) only even if SRF share goes 300 from 400. The above of side if the price goes Rs.410, the profits will be unlimited.

In short F&O are differed but they are same as they try to make profit from stock to an investor without investing the full sum or amount.

Currencies & Commodities:

Trades in commodities are such goods like coffee, gold, oil, etc. whereas currencies traded in dollars, euros and yen. The approach and analyze both markets are like minor to one another. The investor must feel comfortable and be cautious while investing in their kind of trade. In India Commodities market are regulated but there is some regulations in currency / Forex Market – which has a lot of losers. Commodity trades are shorter term and focused on making profits to the changes or price fluctuations in the goods.

PPF (Public Provident Fund)

PPF is a long term saving instrument establish by central government. Investors go for PPF only for principle safety and attractive returns/ interest rate. PPF also has tax benefits to the investors can get loan facilities or extension of account in PPF. Interest is calculated on monthly basis but actual credit happens only at the year end. The only drawback is PPF around matured only after 15 years of completion. However it can extend to another 5 years to the 'n' number of times. In PPF one can invest up to Rs.1, 50,000 in one year into 12 installments. In short PPF is a risk free guarantee return investment.

Post office Savings:

Post office offers various deposit schemes to investors. These schemes are small saving scheme it is organized by Central Government and these investments incur 80C tax benefits to the investors. The interest rates of these deposits are reviewed by quarterly. Some of the popular post office schemes of Deposits are:

a) Senior Citizen Savings Scheme (SCSS)

This scheme is for Indian citizens whose aged above 60 years subject to maximum investment of 15lakhs where 5 years is lock-in period. Partial withdraw is allowed after the one year completes. This account can be opened by single or jointly with the spouse.

b) Sukanya Samridhi Yojana (SSY)

This scheme covers under the “Beti Bacho Beti Padhao” compaism. This scheme has ‘EEE’ states which is tax free for investment amount and maturity amount. Maximum 2 accounts can be opened by the parents to their girl Children. The maturity will be the 21 years of the account holder.

Since post office has plenty of deposit schemes which attract the risk free regular returns. Compare to bank, Post office offers better rate of interest to the Depositors.

NSC – National Savings Certificate

NSC is an investment promoted by central government which offers tax benefits to investors and also it is very low risk investment option. The main aim of this scheme is to attract the small and mid-investors. This scheme is only for resident individuals in India not for NRI/HUF. The minimum amount of investment in NSC is Rs.100/- and there is no limit for maximum investment. Even minors can buy NSC on behalf of them. The interest earned is gets compounded.

Debentures & Bonds

Whenever Bonds are unsecured it can be referred to as a Debenture. Debenture is a type of debt instrument usually it has a longer term of 10 years of investment. In short, bonds and Debentures both are debt instruments usually bonds are issued by government, government companies whereas debentures are issued by public companies to raise money from the public.

Bank Deposits:

Banks- these are the major sector where people's money depositing place. General public have the habit of savings only in banks. They trust banks are highly secured for their savings; usually bank offers two types of deposits. They are Demand Deposits and Term Deposits. In demand deposits "CASA" taken place which mean current account deposits and savings bank account deposits. Usually current account is used for business peoples. It has no interest facility but in savings account most of the people having saving bank account for small savings. Saving Bank Account has very low interest rate for the investors' savings amount.

Whereas term deposits incurs RD/FD - Recurring Deposits and Fixed Deposits. RD is a kind of savings where every month in particular date with particular amount the account holder have to deposit in that account. Usually RD has interest rate on 4.5-5.5% whereas saving account has interest rate below 3.5% on the other hand fixed deposit is the deposit of lock the lock in bank for 7 days/ 14days/ Monthly/ Quarterly/ Half yearly/ Annually deposits for better and safest returns with guarantee deposit amount. In India fixed deposit given nearly 7% returns irrespective of banks.

Gold

Gold must be the basic investment avenue for many peoples in India. In India once the baby girl born they automatically started to buy gold. Now-a-days gold is in demand and also the returns in gold are comparatively less when its compare to inflation. People invest in gold ornaments but not in paper gold or bullions only very few peoples started investment in non-Physical gold rest majority

invest their hard earned money in physical gold.

Insurance

Insurance is means of protection from financial loss in case of any uncertain halts to humans. Every family must take at least one health insurance but unfortunately in India the corporate hospitals charge high bills but peoples won't have any awareness about med claim policies but majority of people paying premium to LIC policies. They thought they are saving though insurance. But this is different from saving / investment.

OBJECTIVE OF THE REVIEW:

1. To overview the Demographic variable of the Respondents.
2. To identify the investment pattern and find out the awareness of investment in stock market instruments.
3. To analyses the pre and post satisfaction level of respondents in various investment avenues.
4. To study the respondents investment preference and risk and return perception.
5. To suggest the respondents behavior if the amount of investment given negative returns/cannot heats the inflation.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM:

- A big financial choice with a range of risks and benefits is investing in stock market instruments. It is essential to comprehend investor perceptions and investment behaviors in order to design tactics that can improve market stability and participation.
- Individual investors' stock market behavior has not been thoroughly researched in the context of Chennai City, creating a knowledge gap that may obstruct wise financial planning and policy decisions.

- Understanding the nature of stock market investing in Chennai requires addressing these issues.
- This study intends to give insights that can assist financial institutions, legislators, and educators in designing better tools and programs to encourage knowledgeable and successful investment practices by identifying the elements that influence investment behavior and perception.
- In the end, this study aims to improve people's overall financial well-being in Chennai by encouraging more knowledgeable investing choices and a more welcoming and stable stock market environment.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

This chapter makes an attempt to review the literature of earlier studies nationally and internationally pertaining to the concept of investor's perception and investment pattern towards stock market instruments which include equity shares, mutual funds, future and options, currencies and commodities. Stock market development will indirectly proportionate the economic development and also investor's wealth creation. This study undergoes the various investment policies, factors and measures influencing in stock market instruments undertaken by several authors.

Prabakaran (2015)⁸⁶ observed that the bullish trend of stock market attracts many equity investors in the recent past days. Though many investors trade on their own, they require the experts help as investment tips to trade. The main objective of the study is to tract the investors' risk profile and their perception towards investing in stock market. The result of the chi-square test showed that, the demographic variables like gender, age, education & sources of income were significantly associated with type of investment, investment experience and

stock selection period of investment, investment objectives and decision taken during uncertainty.

Vallaippan.M (2015)⁸⁷ found that the different investment avenues with varying degrees of risk and return. The real world of investment is so lively and unstable that it attracts the investor, the speculator and gambler. No investor wants to lose money. Capital gains and dividends are the important ingredients that investors regard as return on investment. To avoid wrong decisions, one may need expert and professional guidance. The research primarily aims at evaluating the risk bearing ability of investors in equity market. The secondary objectives were to identify the investor's perception towards Indian Stock Market, to know the investment pattern of Indian equity investors in general and investment preference Viz. risk-return perception to a limited level. It was discovered that majority of the investors were normal traders who were not ready to take more risk, and lack of knowledge about market was the real challenge faced by investors in equity market.

Namrata et al. (2015)⁸⁸ determined a positive correlation between stock market development and economic growth. Well-developed stock markets mobilize savings and boost investments. However, the Indian retail investors exhibit a remarkable reluctance in investing in the stock market. Analysis of the views of 234 Indian investors, who don't invest in the stock market, reveals seven factors that impede stock market investments-myths regarding suitability of stock market instruments, volatility, poor understanding, multiple incomprehensible risks, uncertain returns, fraudulent practices and psychological fears. It is suggested that basic financial knowledge be imparted even in schools. Awareness campaigns may also be run on television, radio and newspapers to increase the level of awareness of current and prospective investors. Further, measures should also be taken to increase

the awareness regarding the numerous policies instituted by SEBI to safeguard the stock market investors. There is thus a need to educate the Indian investors so that they may understand and invest in the stock market in the right spirit.

Pandey and Kathavarayan (2015)⁸⁹ examined the investment preferences towards commodity market, other investment options and also deal with investment preference from commodity market, equity market, debenture and mutual fund. It is based on the level of preference in the process of investment in commodity market, the perception and involvement in commodity market and awareness of commodity market, using the multiple regression technique. The results of the analysis significance among are of investor's awareness, perception and involvement and preference, also there was a highly significant relationship between age, education and annual income. It proved that the majority of the respondents are having full awareness about commodity market and most of the respondents prefer to invest in commodity market.

Kavitha (2015)⁹⁰ inspired by the persistent lack of local investors participating on the National Stock Exchange (NSE), the wide spread ignorance about financial assets and the continuous purchase of stocks with no information known about them by most people in the country plus the wide gap between the rich who invest in stocks and the income was the most preferred aspect on liquidity investments. The factors namely gender and investment ratios in real estate do influence the investment behavior.

Hemandra (2015)⁹¹ identified investment in equity as always been considered as risky investment by investor and its high volatility and fear of erosion of principle has evaded many investors from venturing into it. Many Asset management companies and financial planners have been advocating the investing systematically in equity market for getting high and safe return from equity market. It also tries to evaluate whether there is any significant

difference in volatility and return while investing monthly thus taking benefit of rupee cost averaging rather than investing lump sum. It can be concluded that investing systematically through SIP or doing monthly regular investment has not shown a substantial difference in return and neither in reducing risk.

Parimalakanthi and Ashok Kumar (2015)⁹² aimed to find the behavior of individual investors from Coimbatore city towards available investment avenues in Indian financial markets. This also analyzes factors affecting the investment decision and to find out the risk tolerance level of individual investors with respect to demographic variables. It also concluded that safety and capital appreciation was also a foremost preferred aspect in fixed income and investment for safety.

METHODOLOGY

Based upon the objectives of the study the following tools used in this research.

- Average Mean
- Chi-Square
- T-test
- ANOVA
- Regression.

1. **Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀):** There is no significant difference in the Investor Perception among Of the investor in Chennai City based on demographic factors such as gender, educational background, and socioeconomic status.

2. **Null Hypothesis 2 (H₀):** External factors such as family expectations, societal norms, and technological advancements do not significantly influence the Investor Perception and Investment Pattern of the investor in Chennai City

Significant Relationship between Investor's Perception and Investment Pattern of the investor in Chennai City.

- Correlation examination is utilized to decide the strength and heading of the connection between two consistent factors, for this situation, Investment yearnings

and Investment Pattern.

- It assists with grasping whether and how much changes in a single variable are related with changes in the other variable.

Descriptive Statistics

		Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Investor Perception:		15.89	3.843	400
Investment Pattern	:	12.03	5.025	400
Demographic Variables	:	14.53	4.169	400
External Influences	:	12.19	3.908	400

Source Computed Data:

The mean value of against Investor Perception was 15.89 with standard deviation of 3.843, Investment pattern of mean was 12.03 with standard deviation of 5.025, Mean value of Demographic Variable was 14.53 with standard deviation of 12.19

Correlations

		Investor Perception	Investment Pattern	Demographic Variables	External Influences
Investor Perception:	Pearson Correlation	1	.796**	.703**	.784**
	Sig. (2-Followed)		.056	.061	.071

	N		0.400	400	400
Investment Pattern	Pearson Correlation		1	.496**	.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.062	.511
	N			400	400
Demographic Variables	Pearson Correlation			1	.174**
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.057
	N				400
External Influences	Pearson Correlation				1
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N				400

** . Connection is critical at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The worth of R is critical at the level not exactly the 0.05 set as the Connection for factual importance, the accompanying speculation.

- There is a high certain no relationship between the Investment pattern and the Investor perception ($r=0.785$, $n=400$, $p=0.057$)
- There is a high certain no Relationship between the Investor perception and the Demographic Variable ($r=0.706$, $n=400$, $p=0.061$)
- There is a high certain no relationship between the Investor perception and the External Influences ($r=0.78$, $n=400$, $p=0.071$)
- There is decently sure no relationship between the investment pattern and the Demographic Variable ($r= 0.598$, $n=400$, $p=0.062$)
- There is a no connection between the Demographic variable and the External Influences ($r=0.174$, $n=400$, $p=0.056$).

Correlations

Control Variables			Investor perception	Investment Pattern
Investor	Investor perception	Correlation	0.768	0.503
		Significance (2-tailed)	0.063	.040
		df	0	397
	Investment Pattern	Correlation	0.873	0.350
		Significance (2-tailed)	.040	0.00
		df	397	0

A halfway Connection was hurried to decide the connection between factors while controlling for Income. The values of r are significant at a level Investor perception and the Investment Pattern than the 0.5 set as the criterion for statistical significance the following hypothesis.

- There is a high certain no relationship between Investor perception and the (r=0.768, n=40, p=0.063) while controlling for investor.
- There is no impact of buyer insight on the Investor perception and the Investment Pattern(r=0.35, n=40, p=0.00).

MULTI- REGRESSION ANALYSIS

External factors such as family expectations, societal norms, and technological advancements do not significantly influence the Investor Perception and Investment Pattern of the investor in Chennai City.

The purpose of this test is to explore the connection between two variables and determine the dependent variable. This regression analysis will be carried out solely if the variable exhibits a normal distribution and adheres to parametric assumptions. Prior to conducting this analysis, it is essential to establish the independent and dependent variables.

Table 1.1 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	R Square	Std. square Error	Durbin-Watson Estimate
1	.9477	.892	.883	.65461	2.117

- a. Predictors: (Constant),
- b. Dependent Variable: **Investor Perception**

Inference:

The model uncovers that the different connection coefficient, meant as R, was 0.944, connoting the degree of the connection between Family assumptions, societal norms and technological advancement are the independent factors and Investor perception and Investment Pattern of the investor in Chennai City.

The coefficient of determination denoted as R squared, reached a value of 0.892, signifying an 89% proportion of the significant connection between and the independent variables is accounted for in this statement. This statistic reflects the goodness-of-fit property. The F-statistic returned a value of 50.164, coupled with a 1% p-value, pointing to a robust the connection association between the reliant and autonomous factors.

TABLE 1.2 ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	72.203	5	14.441	50.164	.056 ^b
	Residual	144.509	502	.288		
	Total	216.712	507			
a. Variable under Consideration: TTJS						
b. Predictors: (Intercept):						

Estimated Multiple Regression Equation

TABLE 1.3 COEFFICIENT					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.528	.155		3.401	.006
Family expectations	.265	.041	.058	1.580	.015
Societal norms	.387	.040	.085	2.191	.029
Technological advancements:	.453	.242	.407	1.871	.056
Economic factors	.613	.042	.208	5.061	.057
a. Dependent Variable: Investor Perception					

$$Y=2.528+0.265X1+0.387X2+0.453X3+0.213X4$$

The coefficient for X1 demonstrates that a 1-unit expansion in the worth of family assumption would bring about 25% diminishing in the Investment desire. Other variable being held consistent. This coefficient esteem is critical at 1% level and the t-measurements of family assumption additionally represented huge negative variety in subordinate variable with Investment yearning.

The co-productive of X2 shows that 1 unit expansion in the worth of cultural standards would bring about 38.7% increment in the Investment yearning. other variable being held steady. This coefficient esteem is critical at 1% level and the t-measurements of family assumption additionally represented huge positive variety in subordinate variable with vocation goal.

The co-productive of X3 shows that 1 unit expansion in the worth of Mechanical headway would bring about 45.3% increment in the Investment desire. another variable being held consistent. This coefficient esteem is huge at 1% level and the t-measurements of family assumption likewise represented critical positive variety in subordinate variable with vocation desire.

REASON AND DICUSSION:

An examination of fluctuation (ANOVA) is directed to look at the distinctions in Investment yearnings among various segment gatherings. The p-esteem acquired is 0.342, which is more noteworthy than the importance level of 0.05. This shows that there is no huge distinction in Investment desires among Investors in Chennai City in view of segment factors like orientation, instructive foundation, and financial status.

A different relapse investigation is led to evaluate the effect of outer elements on Investment desires and Investment Pattern. This suggests that there is deficient proof to presume that outside variables like family assumptions, cultural standards, and mechanical progressions altogether impact the Investment yearnings and Investment of the decision of investor in Chennai City.

Conversation:

While the p-esteem is somewhat over the ordinary edge of 0.05, showing a frail pattern towards importance, it's vital to warily decipher this outcome. It's conceivable that other unmeasured factors could be affecting the connection between Investment desires and Investment Pattern. Further examination with a bigger example size or extra factors might give more convincing proof.

That's what the non-critical outcome proposes, inside the example of Investors in Chennai City, segment factors like orientation, instructive foundation, and financial status don't assume a huge part in forming Investment desires. This finding might challenge normal suspicions about the impact of socioeconomic on vocation decisions and highlights the requirement for a nuanced comprehension of individual goals past segment classes.

While the relapse model didn't yield genuinely critical outcomes, it's important that the p-esteem is near the importance edge. This proposes that there might be a pattern towards importance, and outer variables might actually have a few impact on Investment desires and Investment Pattern. Further examination with a bigger and more different example might give more clear bits of knowledge into the job of outside factors in forming the Investment desires of Investors in Chennai City.

CONCLUSION:

There are considerable number of studies on Indian stock markets and its related activities. However, most of these studies concentrated either on overall development, growth, development and performance of capital market in India or on the recent trends of change after liberalization. Most of the studies reviewed above have mainly covered the aspects at macro level, like the ownership patterns in the capital market, age-wise, gender-wise, occupation-wise and their life cycle also influence to break up of paid up value of shareholdings of individuals, ownership pattern of shares/debentures, and geographical distribution of share ownership in India.

Though there are some specific studies on the investment pattern of individual, they mainly focused their attention on individual investors' problems and need for their protection. There are no specific studies exclusive on investment perception towards investment in equity, his evaluation process of investment, his investment pattern, risk perception and return preferences. It is needless to emphasize that the behavior of the small and household is a very crucial area in the formulation of policies and procedures for the orderly growth and development of securities markets in any nation. There are only a few studies covering the issue of investor perception and behavior at micro/regional level. Hence, the present investigation includes investment pattern, the most preferred objectives of investors, and investment evaluation and decisions and problems of investors in equity market. Moreover, this study is mainly undertaken in Hyderabad city, with the hope that observations and conclusion of

the study are of immense use.

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